

**Stability Constants of Metal Complexes
of 1,2,4-Triazoles**

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THE present study reports the stability constants of the metal complexes using bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn with 4-amino-3-(methylphenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (1), 4-amino-3-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (2), 4-amino-3-(*p*-chlorophenoxy-methyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (3), 4-amino-3-(phenoxy-methyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (4).

TABLE I—STABILITY DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES OF 1,2,4-TRIAZOLES (1-4)

Ligand no.	Mn ^{II}			Fe ^{II}			Co ^{II}		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
1	3.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	13.7	9.4	23.1
2	2.8	—	—	5.0	—	—	6.0	2.1	8.1
3	3.4	—	—	4.9	1.4	6.3	5.9	1.7	7.6
4	2.3	—	—	3.0	1.2	4.2	4.0	2.7	6.7
Ligand no.	Ni ^{II}			Cu ^{II}			Zn ^{II}		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
1	14.5	12.7	27.2	15.2	14.5	29.7	14.7	9.4	24.1
2	13.0	5.4	18.4	14.0	12.9	26.9	8.5	5.3	13.8
3	5.9	3.8	9.7	10.2	5.9	16.1	10.2	5.3	15.5
4	4.0	2.7	6.7	4.0	3.0	8.0	3.5	1.5	5.0

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. The ligands (1,2,4-triazoles) were prepared by the literature methods¹ and their solutions (0.01 M) prepared in ethanol. The metal solutions (0.001 M) and NaOH (0.1 M) were prepared in CO₂-free double-distilled water and standardised.

pH measurements were carried out with an Elico LI-120 pH meter, calibrated at 28°.

The procedure involved the titration of the following carbonate-free solutions (total volume 50 ml) against standard NaOH (0.1020 M): (i) 5 ml 0.01 M nitric acid + 3 ml ethanol + 15 ml water, (ii) 1 ml 0.01 M ligand solution + 5 ml 0.01 M HNO₃ + 29 ml ethanol + 15 ml water, and (iii) 1 ml 0.001 M metal solution + 1 ml 0.01 M ligand solution + 5 ml 0.01 M HNO₃ + 29 ml ethanol + 14 ml water. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.05 M using KNO₃.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants (K_L) of the ligands were obtained from the formation curves of the proton-ligand system by plotting $\bar{n}_A$ values against pH. From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values were calculated² at various pH values. Proton-ligand formation constants (log K_L) for the ligands becomes equal to the pH corresponding to $\bar{n}_A=1.5$.

From the titration curves of solutions of (ii) and (iii), $\bar{n}$ and P_L values were calculated². Metal-ligand formation constants of the complexes were calculated applying least-square method² to the $\bar{n}$ and P_L data (Table I) and the formation curves were drawn. The data (Table I) show that the difference between log K₁ and log K₂ values are small and the ratio of log K₁/log K₂ is positive in all the cases. The stability of the complexes increases upto copper followed by a lower value for zinc independent of the nature of the ligand used³ (Fig. 1) with increase in atomic number.

The overall stability of the metal chelates observed with all the 1,2,4-triazoles were Mn^{II} < Fe^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}, which is in harmony with the Irving-Williams order⁴. This indicates that the nature of chelation and the type of bonding in the chelate may be similar in all the metal ions studied.

Fig. 1. Stability of metal complexes of the 1,2,4-triazoles (1-4) as a function of atomic number: (O) 1, (x) 2, (Δ) 3 and (□) 4.

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